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Improving the Methodology of Development of Quantitative Relationships in Preschool Educational Educators

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***Abstract:** In the process of preschool education, the main goal is to use didactic game methods that ensure the formation of skills in the development of quantitative relations in preschool children, and to develop new game methods. depending on the order in which students implement quantitative relations in the educational process, how they use quantitative relations in their activity processes, the skills of developing quantitative relations, the implementation of actions in their place to achieve the desired result It is aimed at forming the ability to think freely. Research object. Payariq District, Samarkand Region 12-DMTT in preschool educational organizations 184 children are receiving education, 98 of them are their parents. Textbook, "Tafakkur" publishing house. Tashkent - 2019, page [157. 37] is engaged in finding ways to avoid excessive stress, which can cause general fatigue, and studying the laws and possibilities of mental development of children of preschool age. Preschool educational organizations published scientific methodological works intended for students, educational games for preschoolers manual and articles, forms reflecting quantitative relations, method and tools. Early mathematical ideas of preschoolers effective method of using mathematical games in formation and learning methods.*

***Key words:** children methods, integration, game, didactic game, develop and achieve, ability.*

INTRODUCTION

The introduction highlights that a pupil's mathematical ability is not innate but develops through conscious effort, especially during the preschool years, when cognitive processes like speech, memory, and thinking grow rapidly. Early childhood, particularly between ages 6-7, is a critical period for learning key skills, including math.

The text emphasizes that games play a vital role in children's mental development, helping them understand the world around them and fostering skills like generalization and abstraction. Educational methods in preschool should focus on structured activities and games to help students form elementary mathematical ideas. Teachers should break down tasks into manageable parts to aid children's gradual mastery of these concepts, with consistency being key to their understanding.

Ultimately, fostering a child's perception, sensory feelings, and mathematical imagination through educational games is essential for their intellectual growth. The ability of each pupil depends on his individual psychological characteristics. Mathematical ability cannot be innate, because innate is an anatomical and physiological characteristic of a person. Mathematics is a special type of ability that depends on the inherent quality of consciousness and develops in the process of mathematical activity. Preschool age is considered the most favorable period for the development of abilities. Mathematics is one of the few subjects that covers different aspects of the personality of students. During the formation and learning of elementary mathematical ideas, all cognitive processes actively develop in preschool children: speech, thinking, memory, perception, feeling. A very important stage of development in a student's life is the early and pre-school period. Pupils develop rapidly, especially during preschool age. Because in the first 6-7 years of a child's life, he achieves a lot. He learns to look and listen, pick up objects and move with them, stand, walk, etc. During this time, he acquires dozens of skill secrets: holding a fork and spoon, working with scissors, a brush, a pencil, writing and reading letters with a pen and other educational tools, observing the environment and giving feedback, reading, discovers many other things for zi. He gathers a lot of information about natural phenomena, sounds, colors, memories of his past and present life and learns to narrate them. He knows the rules of behavior. Recognizes space and time, number and actions.

In order for each student to develop mentally correctly from a young age, he needs conditions of education that teach him the daily useful things of a healthy lifestyle and leave positive images in his memory. The game is very important for children and it is very valuable for them. If the daily life of the student does not include useful and interesting games that sharpen the mind, as we mentioned above, he will not be able to develop quickly and well. Children older than three years reflect the lives of the people around them in their games.

METHODS

According to the tasks set in the research, electronic information training for the educational process of preschool educational organizations is the result of didactic actions, that is, the education of the students of preschool educational organization. Classification of academic subjects according to the educational concept, the component of the educational content: multimedia didactic classification of all four components of the educational content in the educational process: world process of knowledge about, methods of activity, creative activity and emotional-valuable attitude to reality; scenario development to determine the performance of the structure of multimedia didactic games in the educational process; a graphic approach to the structure of the educational material and the construction of individual trajectories of training based on the student's personal experience; performance of the set of requirements for installations consisting of multimedia didactic games in printed form in the course of the educational process; The work of the trainees helps to improve the mastery of the knowledge in the multimedia didactic structure of the educational process of the block, which helps to implement the statistical methods of data processing. In the structured educational process of multimedia didactic games in the educational process of multimedia didactic games in the process of mastering processes, they require pedagogical work, which controls the teaching process.

The scientificity, systematicity and sequence of teaching arising from the laws, demonstration, appropriateness, awareness and creative activity of learners does not deny compliance with general didactic phenomena [24; 28]. Experiments were carried out to demonstrate the implementation of multimedia didactics for the educational processes of pre-school educational organizations. The theoretical and practical preparation of this educational subject and the experience of the educational process were checked by improving the qualification of conducting multimedia didactic games in the educational process. According to the results of the interviews based on the observations and the students, a suitable analysis of the development of competences in the subject being studied was carried out.. The objectivity of the results of the built-in function of multimedia didactic games in the educational process of forming an automated assessment of the students' rating was analyzed by the method of data correlation analysis. In addition, a survey was conducted among professors and teachers of different higher educational institutions in order to evaluate the necessity of using multimedia didactic games in the educational process, in particular, its special functions in the educational process in general, from their point of view. was carried out. Pedagogues who use multimedia didactic games in their work were involved as experts, because their evaluations were related to the textbook built on the basis of the didactic principles described above and having certain functions. Thus, the evaluation of the effectiveness of multimedia didactic games in the educational process structured according to didactic principles includes the following components: - comparative evaluation of the level of theoretical and practical training of students in experimental and control groups; - a comparative assessment of the level of educational motivation of the pupils of the experimental and control groups. Mathematical knowledge of the pupils makes it possible to study the world in a deeper and fuller way without being separated from life. In this, the idea that students have before mathematical concepts is of great importance. Before every news, an idea appears, and then there is a thought about this news. In order to find its decision, the mind compares, examines and, based on them, tries to understand the general method to prove the resulting results and generalize this result³. The process of solving mathematical problems requires independent thinking in its essence. The level of development of mathematical concepts varies from person to person. Its formation requires constant training. These exercises begin with family and preschool education. Each independently solved problem, structured problem, and independent overcoming of the difficulties encountered in the process of solving the problem builds resilience and develops creative abilities. According to psychologists, the problem of forming mathematical concepts is complex and interesting. In its essence, every thought is a product of a positive, low or high level. Each idea is an independent action aimed at research and creation of innovation and its popularization.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

"Elementary mathematics" education and training in training is carried out. Before school education in organizations students with the shape, size and color of objects skills of introduction and correct perception of these properties the issue of development belongs to the field of sensory education. How correct this education is if it is solved, not only the intellectual education of the students, but also the aesthetic, physical and even moral education will be so successful, i.e pupils develop effectively in general. All of the following to a certain extent, it depends on how developed the child's perception is considered of pedagogical education teacher, a feature that differs from all other countries in the world is to create a scientific-research approach in its activities. Researcher The model of a teacher is to regularly analyze his work, his work environment to understand, the results of scientific-research works in his pedagogical activity determine and use it, evaluate the process of independent learning, own development of pedagogical activity according to the results of self-assessment and the ability to recognize the needs of education in our Republic We should introduce it to the system of pre-school

education and primary education. The system of preschool education and primary education of our republic The basis of the Finnish education system is both gifted and dynamic did not exclude all students who need the support of others to offer free alternative ways of raising the level of education introducing the idea. Educator to provide information on educational opportunities implementation through pedagogue and school pedagogue. Pre-school education and primary education in our republic always greet the students, have lunch together, such methods as visiting their teacher-pedagogue and student pay attention to the strengthening of relations between I am here I have listed only a few methods, but I am sure that pedagogues who want to know their students well, of course, there are many more find effective methods, and this ultimately helps them, helps children to learn kindergarten better. Then the whole educational process will become more interesting and training contributes.

The objectivity of the automated assessment of the quality of training in experimental groups, i.e. their rating; - evaluations given by students and pedagogues regarding the tasks of multimedia didactic games in the educational process and the appropriateness of its introduction into the educational process. In the 2023/2024 academic year, 6 academic groups of the 12th DMTT in Samarkand city were selected for experimental work. 3 groups in these groups are prepared according to elementary mathematics). During the academic year, students of some groups studied a course of mathematical analysis with the inclusion of multimedia didactic games (experimental groups) in the educational process, while the rest of the students used only traditional printed publications.

Although they were recommended by the program (control groups), both groups used the same printouts. The numerical composition of the above groups can be seen in the table below.

In the 2023/2024 academic year, 6 students of the 12th DMTT in Samarkand city were selected for experimental work. 3 groups in these groups are trained in elementary mathematics. During the academic year, students of some groups studied a course of mathematical analysis with the inclusion of multimedia didactic games (experimental groups) in the educational process, while the rest of the students used only traditional printed publications. Although they were recommended by the program (control groups), both groups used the same printouts. The numerical composition of the above groups can be seen in the table below. Preschool educational organizations are created for educational processes effectiveness of using multimedia didactic games in the educational process experimental work was carried out in order to show it in practice. education effectiveness of using multimedia didactic games in the process theoretical and practical preparation of students in this subject and was checked by analyzing the level of interest in educational activities.

According to the results of observations and interviews with students, the appropriateness of assessing their competence in the studied subject analysis was carried out. Automated assessment of student ratings multimedia didactic in the educational process of formation objectivity of the results of the work of the built-in function of games was analyzed by the method of data correlation analysis. Besides, education and training between professors and teachers of different higher educational institutions In particular, it is different from multimedia didactic games the need to use functions in the educational process as a whole, they point of view A survey was conducted in order to get an assessment from the point of view. Education in one's workpedagogues who use multimedia didactic games in the educational process were involved as experts, as their evaluations are described above a textbook built on the basis of didactic principles and having certain functions was related to Thus, education is organized according to didactic principles evaluation of the effectiveness of multimedia didactic games in the process is as follows includes components: - theoretical and practical training of students in experimental and control groups comparative assessment of training level; - educational activities of students of experimental and control groups comparative assessment of the level of

motivation; 60 -experience in groups preparation quality pupils the objectivity of the automated assessment, i.e. their rating; - in the process of education by students and pedagogues tasks of multimedia didactic games and their introduction to the educational process evaluations of the appropriateness of the achievement.

Adapted to children in pre-school educational institutions elementary mathematical tasks based on such quantities and relationships when introduced and processed, learning mathematics becomes more effective. Due to excessive precision or formality of elementary mathematical knowledge difficulties that arise do not arise in this case.

Assessment criteria for the experimental and control groups in the 12th DMTT students of the Payariq district of the Samarkand region in the 2023-2024 academic year.

Number of groups		Experience group				Control groups			
Samarkand region	Indicators	The number of students at the beginning of the experiment	%	Number of trainees at the end of the experiment	%	The number of students at the beginning of the experiment	%	Number of trainees at the end of the experiment	%
12-DMTT	Excellent	18	21	24	28	12	15	17	21
	Good	37	43	44	51	31	38	31	38
	All-right	31	36	18	21	39	47	34	41
Total		86	100	86	100	82	100	82	100

12th DMTT, Payariq district, Samarkand region diagram and percentage of test results of students

DISCUSSION

For each motive in both groups, we calculated the mean and variance of motive ratings for the experimental and control groups. Here, we checked not only the homogeneity of the ratings, but also the significance of the differences in the average values, because further research involves comparing the average indicators of the importance of one or another motive. To test the hypothesis of homogeneity of observations, the Chi-square test was used, as in the test of homogeneity of the results of the entrance test of students, except that it is not necessary to group the results of the observations, the calculations are only 7 different values can accept. Student's t test was used to test the hypothesis of significance of differences in sample means. 63 In addition to the analysis of the general educational motivation of the students, the importance of possible internal and external motivations for working with multimedia didactic games in the educational process was analyzed. After processing the questionnaires filled out by the students of the experimental group at the beginning of the semester, it was found that educational and cognitive motives are in the first place in terms of importance for the students: working with multimedia didactic games in the process of education is a course for me. with a maximum of 7 points, it allows to get a positive grade equal to 5.6 points and is evaluated with "...good mastery of the studied subject equal to 5.6 points". In modern conditions, professional motives such as being in demand, getting a diploma according to one's desire, and achieving a career have also become important. It should be said that the questionnaire was conducted before getting to know multimedia didactic games and ways of working with them and their possibilities in the educational process. In the course of education, multimedia didactic games received sufficiently high evaluations regarding the functions such as the possibility of monitoring the individual educational trajectory, getting advice in the process of independent education, and monitoring the personal rating online. Preliminary estimates of possible functions are considered as estimates of students' expectations. For example, an important motive for working with multimedia didactic games in the educational process turned out to be the student's natural desire to spend as little time as possible on completing the task. Reputation motives scored slightly more than two points lower and ranked last in the study of general motivations for educational activities. The evaluations of the motives of working with multimedia didactic games in the educational process are generally lower than the evaluations of the general motives of educational activities, because when the survey was conducted, the students had not yet used multimedia didactic games in the educational process 64 and their Assessments of the functions of multimedia didactic games in the educational process are based, first of all, on the experience and personal assumptions related to the use of computer programs for preparing for entrance tests. The actual estimates of the yin capabilities were obtained at the end of the formative phase of the pilot study, at the end of April 2024. The overall level of academic motivation decreased towards the end of the semester, but this phenomenon is natural and has been noted by many researchers over the years [48]. In the experimental group, the importance of communicative and professional motives increased slightly, but these changes did not affect how the groups of motives were ranked. The increasing importance of communicative motives can be explained by, among other factors, the need to communicate with fellow students in the course of educational activities without the direct participation of the pedagogue. When the motivations for educational activities are divided into internal, external positive and external negative motives, significant differences in the motivational sphere of the students of the experimental and control groups are revealed. The percentage of students of the first and second groups, whose internal motives are the leader in their educational activities, is approximately equal, making up 59% and 57%, respectively, and the redistribution of external positive and external negative motives is more significant. The educational activity of the experimental group of educators is characterized by the fact that the educational activities are controlled by external

negative motives, that is, those who study to avoid condemnation of others, displeasure of parents and other negative factors, have a smaller share. Only 6% of such pupils in the experimental group and in the control group made up 8%. 65 evaluations of the functions of multimedia didactic games in the educational process were distributed in such a way that the difference between the evaluations became more clear and ranking according to the importance of motives can be done more precisely, the average value of most evaluations decreased slightly, only the values of five motives increased. The most valuable for students learning science using multimedia didactic games in the educational process are the educational motives related to mastering science and getting a good grade from it. In this case, the motives have changed their positions according to their importance. In the course of education, the value of multimedia didactic games as a source of information about the student's personal rating in the lecture increased from 3.8 to 4.1, which can be explained by the relevance of this issue on the eve of the exam session. This can also explain why the motive related to fulfilling the requirements of pedagogues as a necessary condition for obtaining a diploma moved to the third place with a score of 5.18. At the end of the semester, the five most important reasons for using multimedia didactic games in the educational process from the point of view of the students are the possibility to get advice during problem solving (increased from 4.6 points to 4.76 points) and the possibility to follow an individual educational trajectory (4.8 from up to 5.09 points) was also included. Opportunities to show parents their success remained among the least important motives, although this indicator increased slightly from 2.8 to 2.9 points, which corresponds to a low level of importance.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a pedagogue in preschool educational organizations organization of the educational process by the educator, that is, the educational process development implies the correct selection of methodical games, so that the little ones it will be possible to fulfill the tasks set before them, but at the same time they requires spending mental energy, development and self-organization will help. With games used in preschool educational organizations getting to know each other in advance, playing in a team and following certain rules helps to acquire skills. In conclusion, it is quantitative in preschool educational organizations development of imagination, perception of the form of things in students.

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